

Data Management plan for the project “Standardization of Modern Latvian Pronunciation” New

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the Fundamental and Applied Research project “Standardization of Modern Latvian Pronunciation”, No. lzp-2024/1-0613.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Standardization of Modern
Latvian Pronunciation

Researchers

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Organizations

Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of
Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data Management plan for the project "Standardization of Modern Latvian Pronunciation" New

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Standardization of Modern Latvian Pronunciation

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-03-31

4. Templates

Descriptions

Manually Annotated Phonetic Dataset

DMP outlines the strategy for managing, storing, and sharing data generated in the project "Standardization of Modern Latvian Pronunciation". The plan details the types of data to be developed, metadata and any relevant annotations. It specifies the formats for data storage.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

A manually annotated phonetic dataset will be developed, by phonetically transcribing at least 1000 frequently used lemmas (about 10,000 wordforms) from the Balanced Corpus of Modern Latvian LVK20227 and other selected corpora of Latvian National Corpora Collection (<https://korpuss.lv>). The dictionary will contain transcriptions in both – International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) and Latvian traditional phonetic alphabet.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Until now, no word frequency list has been created based on modern Latvian language corpora that could be used in the development of the dataset.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data will be useful for researchers, educators and learners of Latvian, general public using the Latvian language – to improve the quality of standard Latvian pronunciation, researchers of computational linguistics and language technology developers.

The dataset it will help validate that The Latvian Phonetic Transcription Concept and The Handbook of Modern Latvian Pronunciation is complete; it will ensure that the most common Latvian words have manually verified correct phonetic transcription in Tezaurs.lv; it will serve as a validation set for the development of the phonetic transcription tool.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

Handle

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

Comment:

No, there will be no embargo period applied. The data will be openly accessible immediately after publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

CLARIN-LV

<https://repository.clarin.lv/repository/xmlui/?locale-attribute=lv>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

To access the data, software tools such as Excel or any spreadsheet software, R, and JASP are needed. These tools will allow users to process, analyze, and visualize the dataset effectively. Additionally, any other data analysis tools compatible with standard data formats (e.g., CSV, Excel) could be used for further analysis and interpretation.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

CSV format will be used

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Roberts Dargis (0000-0001-9375-6410)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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